

Participants Characterization			
Question	Alternatives	Freq	Rel Freq
Role	Fullstack Developer	9	45,00%
	Frontend developer	7	35,00%
	DevOps developer	0	0,00%
	Software Architect	0	10,00%
	Project Leader	2	0,00%
	Mobile	1	5,00%
	Software engineering team leader	1	5,00%
Professional experience working with Micro Frontends	No experience	0	0,00%
	Less than 1 year	1	5,00%
	Between 1 and 2 years	4	20,00%
	More than 2 years	15	75,00%
Currently working with Micro Frontends?	Yes	15	75,00%
	No	5	25,00%